

STATE EDUCATIONAL STANDARDS FOR TEACHING THE FINE ARTS IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS (EXAMPLE OF 5-7TH GRADE STUDENTS)

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses technologies for improving the effectiveness of teaching Fine Arts in general secondary schools, and the content of Fine Arts classes today is related to the state educational standard. In addition, the types of fine arts classes, the tasks and content of fine arts classes, as well as the differences between the classes of fine arts in grades 1-4 and 5-7 are described.

Today, the content of education in general secondary schools is determined based on the goals and objectives of the subject of fine arts and based on state standards of education. The program of fine arts identifies the following five types:

1. Cognition of being (grades 1-4).
2. Artistic construction (grades 1-4).
3. Basics of art criticism (grades 5-7).
4. Descriptive by nature (grades 1-7).
5. Compositional activity (grades 1-7).

Perception of being plays an important role in the development of students' aesthetic perception, taste, understanding, imagination and memory in this area. Cognition of the being is usually carried out before the performance of thematic compositions, which involves the ability to see the elegance and beauty of

nature and the environment, the use of impressions of perception in practical artistic and creative activities. Also, during the trip to nature, if necessary, some objects and events are sketched with the help of pencils, paints and other artistic materials.

In such lessons, children observe plants, animals, birds, fish in the classroom and outside the classroom, get an idea of the appearance of nature in different seasons, the mood (happy, sad, thoughtful, etc.). Observing and talking about beings in elementary school helps students learn more about some of life's events. It also allows you to develop important qualities, such as a certain amount of analysis and generalization of the shape, structure, color of things.

In the process of observing nature and being, children are taught to love and care for it. During nature trips, children are

explained that some aspects of them vary depending on the seasons. It also develops children's spatial imagination and focuses on plan, linear and aerial perspectives. Children's consciousness is informed that the observation of the creature is directly related to the visual creative activity, it is impossible to perform quality visual work without knowing the creature.

In accordance with the tasks of cognitive training, it is planned to conduct the following trainings:

1. To study the peculiarities of nature in autumn, winter and spring;
2. Observation of flowers, insects, ornamental fish and birds;
3. Get acquainted with the wonders of nature, spring and autumn works, etc.

As mentioned above, the purpose of such activities is to teach children to know the existence, the peculiarities of things and events in it, in particular, the structure, shape, color, size, proportions, spatial conditions, their changes depending on the seasons. is to achieve awareness. If it is not possible to observe the objects to be studied in nature, the teacher achieves his goal by showing children in the classroom reproductions, slides, photographs of works of art.

In order to increase the interest and creativity of students in the lessons of fine arts in the primary school and to acquaint them more widely with the various materials used in painting, artistic construction work is also carried out.

For this interesting type of visual activity, the program includes special hours, which further enrich the content of the lessons. There are three main materials used in construction:

1. Art materials (colored paper, foil, wallpaper, plastic, clay, etc.);
2. Natural materials (leaves, branches, roots, bark, seeds of fruits and vegetables, colored stones, stalks of wheat and barley, etc.);
3. Discarded materials (synthetic containers free of beverages and medicines, matchboxes, foam, foam, lids, etc.).

In art construction, children develop skills such as working with scissors, gluing with glue, folding papers according to the shape of things, wrapping, bringing some artistic waste and natural materials together, creating an image by adding. The development of these skills involves the completion of a number of tasks in the primary school curriculum. They include:

Drawing of pencils, boxes, balloons, flags, teapots, bowls, cars, planes, rockets, etc. of different shapes on colored paper and cardboard;

Insects – the formation of golden beetles, dragonflies, butterflies, etc. by cutting colored paper;

Production of hanging toys by cutting, folding and gluing colored paper;

Creating images of fish, insects, birds, animals using natural materials;

Work on colored paper, art and discarded materials, applications, collages, meaningful compositions in a mixed way (for example, "On the street", "At the Cosmodrome");

Discarded materials – wire, yarn, hemp, pieces of fabric, plastic containers, matchboxes, foam, foam, container lids for simple transport (boat, spinach, car, tractor, etc.), birds (swallows), parrot, goose, sparrow, stork, duck, save, etc.), toys

of animals (fox, wolf, rabbit, bear, tiger, dog, lion, etc.) image processing;

Preparation of the image of dried leaves, colored paper, a flower opened by means of branches, a branch of a flowering tree, etc.;

One of the most important tasks in artistic construction is to know the specifics of artistic, discarded materials (hard, soft, brittle, flexible, heavy, light, hungry, dark, etc.) and to work with them. It is necessary to correctly determine the proportions of measurement and measurement, structure, shape, color.

It is also necessary to know the teaching aids and materials used in construction, to distinguish between natural, artistic and discarded materials.

Being able to see the form of things is also a task of this type of artistic activity. When doing such work, they are also taught to keep the workplace clean and tidy.

The department of basics of art criticism is one of the most important parts of the subject. It has its own system of educational tasks in the program as an independent department in grades 5-7, and it consists of materials of fine, applied, decorative and architectural arts. The purpose of this section is to help students to consciously understand and evaluate works of art, to understand its importance in society and people's lives.

The department of basics of art criticism promotes the aesthetic development of the student's personality, acquaints him with the beauties of life around him through the great masterpieces of world culture and works of art, forms his artistic taste, teaches him to love art.

In the classes on the basics of art criticism, students are introduced to the classical cultural heritage, its great traditions and the service of art to the people, the various currents and trends in art. concepts are formed.

Educational materials on the perception of works of fine and applied arts are associated with the practical work of students. Showing children copies of works of art and their analysis arouses students' interest in art and directs them to this field. During the presentation of works, children are introduced to the idea, the main idea and the artistic means used.

About the basics of decorative and applied arts in the lessons of applied arts, folk arts and crafts, Uzbek folk arts and crafts, costumes, national costumes of Uzbek and foreign people's knowledge, acquaintance with the tools and materials used by folk masters.

As for the art of architecture, to give an idea of the art of architecture and its connection with the environment, beauty in architecture, expediency, individual and social architecture, acquaintance with their types, the interrelation of the function and their aesthetic solution, the nature of the decorative ornaments on the facade and interior, the main terms used in architecture. The nature of the exterior and interior art decorations of the buildings, as well as the materials used in them, are also introduced.

To perform these tasks, the oldest architectural monuments in the territory of Uzbekistan, the architecture of Uzbekistan IX-XIX centuries, the architecture of the Renaissance in the East and the West, the modernity of Uzbekistan and the world. There are classes on architecture.

As stated in the state educational standards of fine arts, it is intended to provide children with knowledge of the basics of art criticism:

1. Fine art is a kind of art and its place and importance in people's lives. Development of fine arts in the territory of Uzbekistan (samples of fine arts found in Afrosiyob, Varakhsha, Toprak kala and other places). Types and genres of fine arts (painting, graphics, sculpture) and genres (landscape, life, still life, portrait, historical, batal, animal, legend, marina). Types of paintings - bench painting, monumental painting, miniature painting. Painting techniques - frescoes, mosaics, stained glass.

2. Types of sculpture - bench sculpture, decorative sculpture, monumental sculpture; Relief (bas-relief, high-relief); round sculptures.

3. Types of graphics - bench graphics, stamp, poster, book graphics; newspaper-magazine graphics; propaganda and agitation graphics; labels, packaging, and so on.

4. Movaraunnakhr Miniature School; Oriental miniature schools. Renaissance Fine Arts in Europe; Contemporary Fine Arts of Uzbekistan; Modern advanced fine arts of the world; mainstream trends in world fine arts; the world's largest museums of fine arts; The largest museum of fine arts in Uzbekistan. The life and work of the world's greatest artists (Kamoliddin Behzod, Leonardo da Vinci, Ural Tansikbaev, Chingiz Akhmarov and others).

At present, the creation of state educational standards in each subject, including the arts and aesthetics, and its approval by the government is an event of great scientific and practical significance.

These standards are the first in the history of Uzbekistan, which will create conditions for the organization of education in schools of the country on a high scientific and methodological basis and bring it to the level of world standards.

The standard allows for the correct and flawless implementation of the requirements of the state, as well as the elimination of shortcomings and deficiencies in the existing program, textbooks and manuals, as well as the organization of the level of training requirements. will give. It also serves as a key document for organizations that oversee school education.

According to the state standard, the content of fine arts education in primary school is described in the following four areas: perception of being; artistic construction; description according to nature; compositional activity.

In grades 5-7, it is reflected in the following three areas:

1. Basics of art criticism;
2. Depiction by nature;
3. Compositional activity;

In teaching the subject of fine arts in these areas, each teacher must know what to focus on. The main points that a teacher should pay attention to when teaching fine arts are:

1. To teach students to see, comprehend, enjoy and appreciate the subtleties of being (around) and works of art.
2. Orientation of children to creative, abstract, logical thinking, especially the development of creative abilities and fantasies.

3. To provide theoretical, but general, elementary knowledge in the field of fine, applied, architectural arts.

4. To develop in students such qualities as observation, visual memory, estimation, spatial imagination, which are important for the person.

5. Development of fine skills in painting and sculpture.

6. Nurture and develop an aesthetic sense.

7. Cultivate interest in art and cultivate love.

These tasks require that every teacher who teaches Fine Arts at school be an expert. This is because the standard content is designed for professional teachers.

The state standard of education in fine arts reflects the content of three types of art -

fine, applied and architectural arts. Knowledge of the life and work of Uzbek masters of fine, applied and architectural arts, the centers where these types of art are developed in Uzbekistan, the largest art museums in Uzbekistan is one of the tasks of the subject of fine arts. notes. The purpose of this is to provide students with artistic education through the national art, as well as the aesthetic, moral and labor education of the individual. The aim of teaching the national Uzbek art more broadly and deeply than the modern advanced art of foreign countries and the world is that every Uzbek student should know the history and literature of his people. is to achieve a relatively broader knowledge of the horse as well. National art should be the basis of education.

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